

The Migration of Korean Hanok Interior Design and Filipino Bahay Kubo as a Model for Sustainable Community Spaces

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Abstract

The interior focuses on the migration of the Korean Hanok village and the Filipino Bahay Kubo for the cultural village located in Batuan, Carmen, Bohol. The space utilizes a passive cooling technique. The village is open to multi-cultural, where it offers an interfaith room. The spaces focus on introducing the Korean culture in Bohol Island, as the place is a growing tourism area. It is located near the Chocolate Hills Viewpoint, which is famous amongst the tourists that making it the perfect opportunity to introduce something new to the tourists coming to the Philippines from all over the world.

Keywords

Bahay Kubo, Hanok, sustainable , passive cooling, bamboo, cultural preservation, SDGs, community space.

Research Agenda Alignment

Sustainable Development Goals

- 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities
- 12 Responsible Consumption and Production
- 13 Climate Action

USC Research Agenda

- Cultural Heritage and Preservation
- Sustainable Built Environment

Introduction

The Korean Hanok Village and the Bahay Kubo both harmonize with nature, and with their similar functions, passive cooling, and protection from wildlife. The goal of this project is to introduce the Korean culture in Bohol, Philippines. The Bahay Kubo is a square-shaped house with no divisions, which is recognized as the national house of the

Philippines that uses bamboo and nipa as its primary materials (Bureau of Public Works, 1920). The Korean Hanok Village also has similarities with the bahay kubo which is has a modular and open interior. These days, many people think that using natural materials are more not durable compared to the modernized materials, where chemicals are mixed into. This project utilizes sustainable materials like bamboo, reclaimed wood, and simple lighting that are available within the area. The goal is to explore how the Bahay Kubo and Korean Hanok Village Interior can be adapted as a design model for the School of Living Traditions that incorporates sustainable principles which including passive cooling, and modular spaces to preserve the Korean heritage while promoting sustainability. It emerges as a powerful example of how traditional knowledge can guide modern practices. It envisions a space where the local communities can gather to preserve and pass down indigenous knowledge and traditions. The bamboo is an ideal material for this project since it is known for its regenerative and absorbing more carbon dioxide compared to other tree species abilities. The cultural village aims to preserve cultural heritage such as weaving, music, and indigenous crafts of both culture. The concept is inspired by the Filipino Bahay Kubo style combined with the Korean Hanok Interior which utilizes wood and white wall. The natural grey stone flooring had been used to balance out the warm color within the space. The use of Capiz Shell for the door, and rattan herringbone helps supporting the Filipino arts. The Jalousie windows has a easy function and is helpful in covering the sunlight when needed, and is often found in the Filipino homes. The layout of the space encourages interaction, community building, and flexibility. The minimal use of concrete and steel helps in reducing leaving carbon footprints and it also shows the importance of preserving the traditions by making it known, with the combination of Korean culture that makes the place unique, and it brings opportunities to contribute to the growing tourism in Bohol.

Through this strategy, it helps economies grow, as well as the traditions that won't be forgotten.

Methods

Figure 1: Design Process

Site Analysis.

Analyzing sun paths, prevailing winds, rainfall, and seismic activity. The researcher must identify the site's slope, elevation, and soil type for the construction to be successful, and map out existing trees, plants, and wildlife to integrate or preserve. The goal is to understand how to naturally cool, ventilate, and light the space using the Hanok and Bahay Kubo concept. The site is located along the road, which makes it accessible to vehicles.

Comparative Study.

It is to identify the materials and functional elements of the Traditional Hanok Interior and Bahay Kubo, and translate them into a hybrid design for community use.

Implementation Strategy.

Using locally sourced materials like bamboo, nipa palm, reclaimed wood that can be sourced around Bohol, and cultural preservation through introducing artifacts, weavings, dances, and music. A place where the guests can learn about different traditions.

Results

1. The proposed design integrates the Sustainable Development Goals, which supports SDG 11, Sustainable cities and communities, by being constructed with readily available local materials. It envisions the Bahay Kubo and Hanok Interior as a flexible and adaptable space, supporting this blend of old and new, making it a resilient model for future education and community development. It supports the SDG 12, Responsible consumption and production, by reducing waste materials, supporting economies, tourism, and tradition. It supports SDG 13, Climate Action, by utilizing natural materials to conserve the environment and avoiding materials that are composed of chemicals and toxins, which are harmful to the environment.
2. The concept of migration of traditional Hanok Village and Bahay Kubo as a model for community spaces was achieved by Following the Hanok Interior while using materials that are being used in making the Bahay Kubo like bamboo, nipa palm, and reclaimed wood maintaining Korean features like the door, and adding feature of Filipino touch in windows and furniture.

With this, the study presents an interior of a migration of Korean and Filipino interior to the community space, bringing the Korean culture into the Philippines. With the use of sustainable materials, passive cooling can be achieved.

Figure 2: Interior Perspective of the Receiving and Social Zone: Atrium.

The design follows a simple Korean Hanok interior blending in the Filipino elements, the rattan herringbone wall, capiz shell, and rattan furniture to keep the balance between the Korean and Filipino interior. The open ceiling atrium brings in natural light.

Figure 3: Interior Perspective of the Community Zone: Marketplace.

Figure 4: Interior Perspective of the Community Zone: Courtyard, Community Plaza.

The design follows a tropical design concept while maintaining the Bahay Kubo and Hanok Village Architectural elements. The village had been designed with a pathway where the guests would be guided into different zones.

Figure 5: Interior Perspective of the Cultural and Reflection Zones: Museum.

Figure 6: Interior Perspective of the Cultural and Reflection Zones: Interfaith Room.

The design envisions a space where each building can accommodate to 10 people per batch, and had been layout in a circulation method to avoid traffic. Each area has an air-conditioner installed, with enhanced natural ventilation, the jalousie windows. This area is known as the quiet zone where the walls had been installed with a acoustic plasterboard which can absorb noises from outside that will not be heard from the outside.

Figure 7: Interior Perspective of the Creative and Performance Zone: Fashion and Performance Hall.

Figure 8: Interior Perspective of the Creative and Performance Zone: Fashion and Performance Hall.

The design of the fashion and performance hall can also be used for events to showcase the Korean performances that brings in unique experiences not only to the tourists, but also to the Filipino locals.

Figure 9: Interior Perspective of the Learning Zone: Sustainability Lab and Library.

The sustainability lab offers a first-hand experience to the guests in experimenting with food by learning to mix biko with yaksik. The furniture had been layout in a classroom and laboratory style. The space had been combined with the mini library where the

guests can source books that may help them in experimenting.

Figure 9: Interior Perspective of the Learning Zone: Culinary Studio and Learning Pavilion.

It is a space designed for cooking where the guests will learn how to cook the combined recipe of Biko and Yaksik. It is provided with the necessary utensils and materials, for it to be possible. The space can accommodate up to 10 guests per batch.

Figure 9: Blow-up View of the lighting installation in faux beam

It is a technique where the recessed downlight can be installed in an open ceiling setting, where the electrical wires will be hidden through the beams. The holes are cut on under side of the beam to house the lights. It uses custom high-density polyurethane wood beams, which are cost-effective and durable, and serve as an alternative to wood that blends in with the mahogany wood used for doors.

Discussion

1. During the process of planning, the first look, the interior looked too Filipino. The Korean Hanok feature was not visible, where the walls had to be changed to white to bring in the balance of the Hanok interior.
2. The incorporation of traditional design into a modern framework illustrates a broader architectural and interior movement toward cultural resilience and place-based identity. The project draws inspiration from the philosophy of *Wabi-Sabi*, valuing impermanence and imperfection, which resonates with the organic, evolving nature

of both Filipino and Korean vernacular structures.

3. The final proposal successfully integrates traditional Filipino and Korean architectural and interior principles. The Filipino influence is seen in the open-plan layout, passive cooling strategies, and material use (bamboo and wood), while the Korean influence is incorporated in spatial balance, low-height furniture, and multifunctional zones.

By identifying the similarities and differences of each interior design allows the researcher to balance out the Korean and Filipino elements within the interior.

Conclusion

This study explored the integration of Filipino and Korean vernacular architecture and interior design that utilizes sustainable practices in the community-oriented spaces. By combining a spatial openness for passive cooling of Bahay Kubo with minimalist of Korean Hanok Interior demonstrates how traditional architecture and interior design can influence the modern design. This project emphasizes the value of cultural preservation through design while maintaining functionality, and sustainability. This also highlights the importance of hybrid as a means to create resilient, and meaningful spaces for cultural exchange, and community development.

End Notes

¹ *Bahay Kubo* – A traditional Filipino stilt house made of native materials such as bamboo and nipa palm, known for its passive cooling design, modular structure, and adaptability to tropical climates. It represents sustainable vernacular architecture in rural Philippine settings.

² *Hanok* – A traditional Korean house characterized by natural materials (wood, clay, stone), and focus on harmony with nature and seasonal adaptation. Its clean lines and symmetrical spatial layout reflect minimalist values.

³ *Passive Cooling* – A design strategy that uses natural ventilation, shading, and thermal mass to maintain comfortable indoor temperatures without relying on mechanical systems, especially effective in tropical and subtropical climates.

⁴ *Faux Beam* – An architectural element made to resemble a structural beam but often hollow or non-load bearing. In this study, faux beams were used to conceal lighting and wiring, combining function with traditional aesthetic appeal.

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